

HOW TO IMPROVE WRITING SKILLS AND BOOST VOCABULARY IN IELTS

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Abstract: This article describes information about improvement writing skills and increasing vocabulary in IELTS test. You can find some effective methods and ways to solve these nuisances.

Key words: method, knowledge, technique, boost, vocabulary, outline.

Аннотация: Данная статья рассматривает информацию о том, как улучшить навыки письма и увеличить словарный запас в тесте IELTS. Можете найти несколько эффективных методов и способов решения данных задач.

Ключевые слова: метод, знание, техника, повышение, словарный запас, план.

Currently, most people have interest in learning English and studying in abroad. So that, they are striving to get IELTS certificate. Many people struggle with the IELTS exam preparation, it is popular with being complex. For a number of people, writing can be the most challenging part of the test. “Upgrading the quality of education in the Philippines by requiring all high school graduates seeking admission to post-secondary degree programs necessitating a minimum of four years` study to pass a national entrance examination and appropriating funds therefor”[1]. Furthermore, they have struggle with vocabulary. So, in this article people who have issues with improving writing and boost vocabulary, can find effective methods and ways.

There are a lot ways and techniques of improving the writing skills and boosting vocabulary [2, P. 58-67]. Firstly, these techniques show how to develop writing skills. Now you are familiar with the ins and outs of the writing section, let’s get into my top tips for performing at your best on test day.

1. Use your time wisely

You get 60 minutes to complete the entire section. Task two contributes more to your score, so I recommend spending no more than 20 minutes on task one and 40 minutes on task two. Include time for planning and checking what you’ve written. It’s good to get into the habit of setting 60-minute time limits when doing practice tests.

2. Check the number of words

You need to write a minimum of 150 words for task one and 250 words for task

two. Anything less and you will lose marks.

3. Understand the task

Read the instructions carefully, and underline or highlight the keywords. Know what questions you need to cover and what information you need to include.

4. Organise your ideas logically

Spend up to five minutes brainstorming ideas and selecting what information you’re going to include. Organise your ideas logically, and include linking words and cohesive devices between paragraphs, sentences and phrases.

5. Check your work!

When you’ve finished each task, always do a thorough check. It helps to ask the following questions.

Next one is how to increase your vocabulary to ace your Speaking test

1. Get an idiom dictionary and learn a few a day

Idioms are phrases that require prior understanding before you can use them in conversations. This is because such phrases are usually not literal and can’t be understood based on the words within each phrase.

Having said that, idioms function in a way that literal meanings cannot. Hence, they play a major role in the progression of language.

As including idioms in your conversation can help you express yourself in a more creative manner, it helps to learn some.

2. Read extensively from newspapers to magazines

One of the fastest ways to improve your vocabulary is to read. Whether it’s the daily newspaper or a bestselling novel, every publication has something to offer!

In the event you chance upon any words or phrases you don’t understand, you can always head to an online dictionary or do a quick Google search to find the meaning.

It helps to write these new words or phrases down and then try to use them when you can in your everyday conversations.

3. Watch the evening news every night

If reading isn’t really your thing, then turn on your TV and make the evening news a part of your daily routine.

By watching the news presenter speak and observing how he or she reports the news, you’ll be able to pick up new words or phrases and notice how they’re weaved in to bring a point across.

Also, if there are any talk shows or TV dramas that you particularly enjoy, you can kill two birds with one stone by watching them too! Of course, you’ll have to be disciplined and remember that you’re doing it to learn and expand your vocabulary, not just for pure entertainment.

4. Read across various disciplines and topics (from tech to family & climate

change)

A good way to increase your vocabulary is to not limit yourself to a certain kind of topic.

When you read across a range of topics, you'll be exposing yourself to different styles and also get to learn how various words play a part to bring ideas to life.

5. Learn synonyms for commonly used words

A key component of the IELTS is to examine the depth of your vocabulary range, so repeating the same word over and over will not do you any favours.

Thus, it helps to learn synonyms, which are basically other variations of common words that are used to describe the same thing.

Doing so would prevent you from going back to the same word. For example, instead of always saying the word “close”, you can replace it with “shut” or “seal” to bring the same point across, depending on the situation.

6. Use more collocations in your conversations

Collocations are important because they can make you sound like a native speaker when you master them.

When you get familiar with collocations, you'll understand how to correctly use common words in a phrase or sentence. For example, the word “take”, which can be used in “take a nap” or “take care”.

In conclusion, learning languages are not easy. Although there are some confusing points, learning language is always helpful in any time [4, P.422-425]. Pay attention for your level and what kind of learner are you while learning. Because if you learn somethings which is higher than your level, may be it is challenging for you. So try to learn new things related to your level. Above I mentioned some useful and the most effective ways which can assist to increase your vocabulary range and improve writing skill. All of them are useful if you use correctly. Most people always should be learning English. Most students seek for new words, and should read a lot of articles and especially scientific articles.

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